

INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract. *The article describes the daily development of the Internet, various trends in the Internet, the positive and negative effects of the Internet on the minds of young people, the fact that they spend their lives in the virtual world, and the youth who are addicted to the Internet.*

Keywords: *internet, visual life, internet addiction, online education, Igromaniya, Nomophobia'.*

INTRODUCTION

What is the Internet?

The Internet is a global computer system connecting large (global) and small (local) computer networks. In it, regardless of geographical location, time and space, some computers and small networks form a global information infrastructure in mutual cooperation.

Is the Internet a good thing or a bad thing?

The Internet is not a thing, but a tool. That is, it is a mediator that is needed to satisfy our needs in our daily life. Moreover, nowadays the Internet has become the main part of our life.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

As we all know, the 21st century is the age of information technology. At the same time, everyone uses mobile phones, computers, and televisions. We use these devices in our daily life, many times a day, that is, we get the necessary information, read, learn, apply it to life, or otherwise give it to our brothers and sisters, our children as toys. Of course, if we use it for good - if we study, if we strive for something, if we work on ourselves, if we gain necessary life experiences for ourselves, it is not without benefits. But, is it better to give phones to our minor children, our brothers and sisters, nieces and nephews who are in kindergarten and elementary school, and make them addicted to the Internet right now?

We are happy when young children play with the phone, watch videos, create something with their fingers, or they already know the phone, they are smart, we say that there were no such technologies in our time. However, we never think that the situation we are laughing at today will cause negative consequences tomorrow. Let's think about it, don't we tie the most cheerful, innocent, simple, unforgettable, sweet moments of our babies to some kind of phone or television so that they don't destroy us or spoil us?

According to the data, in the period from 3 to 5 years, children quickly receive and remember any information. We know that for them the universe is full of various innovations, knowledge and wonders. Unfortunately, many of our parents carelessly look at their children because they are busy with phone and computer games. They forget that there are games that can play with children, which can be spent productively. A one-year-old child knows how to play a game on the phone, but does not know the harm, and we adults are aware of all this and are indifferent. In the end, we do not notice that our children are becoming slaves of various virtual games.

Internet addiction can negatively affect children's healthy development. Families, teachers, and other members of the community must work together to balance Internet use and develop healthy habits in children.

Although Internet addiction is a common condition in society, there is no standard term to describe this phenomenon, because many scientists question the legitimacy of defining it as a separate type of Internet addiction.

A.E. Voyskunsky noted that there are qualitative changes in the approach to the study of the problem in foreign studies at the beginning of the 21st century. Many scientists are wondering whether the Internet itself is a sufficient environment for the formation of addiction, or whether people who are prone to addiction find a way to perform adequate behavior here, and this question is researched and will become the main foundation of all future research involving the Internet as a unique domain of human activity, the personal characteristics of users, and their social environment. A.G. Asmolov, as well as other researchers, point out that the psychological dependence on the object of dependence is formed much earlier than the physiological one.

In 1998-1999, K. Surratt and K. Murray opposed the "medicalization" of Internet addiction, offering an alternative perspective from the point of view of interactionism. According to them, Internet addiction is not a serious problem and socio-culturally it does not differ from other forms of social interaction. Internet use at the level of disease demonetizes this information technology, which casts the user in the role of self-seeking victim.

Many subjects show undifferentiated and excessive demands for themselves and others, which indicates infantile self-esteem. Studying the phenomenon of Internet addiction in groups of students shows that affiliation, communication motives, and feelings of loneliness are positively related to the feeling of discomfort in being separated from the network.

The results of the study suggest a specific type of schizoids in Internet-addicted subjects, according to such criteria as emotional apathy, communication partner, egocentrism, inability to perceive criticism, which is usually related to the results of the study of personality characteristics of young people in Internet addiction.

RESULTS

The virtual world has drawn us deep into its dooby, phones and computers have so shackled us, our body parts, that it is up to us to break free.

According to statistics, in 2021, more than 1.3 million cases of cyber-attacks were observed in the national internet segment.

Internet addiction is a behavioral addiction to using the Internet and excessive use of it, spending a lot of time on the Internet. Internet addiction is not a medically defined mental illness, but includes video game addiction and online gambling addiction. According to the calculations of scientists, more than 50% of the world's population is addicted to the Internet.

The causes of Internet addiction in children can be complex and include a number of factors:

Emotional difficulties: Emotional problems such as stress, anxiety, or depression may cause a child to turn to the Internet as an escape.

Easy Access: The proliferation of mobile devices and the Internet gives children constant access to the online world.

Fun and escape: Children can escape real problems through games or online activities.

Family Relationships: Troubled family relationships can lead children to the Internet world.

Advertisements and attractive content: Advertisements and online content to attract children can increase internet addiction.

Social Isolation: Children may try to meet their needs for friendship and connection online.

The following strategies can be used to treat and prevent Internet addiction in children:

Awareness raising: Teaching children the limits of internet use and encouraging conscious online behaviour.

Family Involvement: Establishing open communication between family members and spending time together.

Social Activities: Orient children to social activities and physical activities such as sports.

Education: Educate children about the benefits and dangers of the Internet.

Time management: Limit online time with children and take regular breaks.

Parental Controls: Use parental controls to control children's access.

Alternative activities: Providing children with alternative ways of entertainment and learning that are not online.

Professional help: In serious cases, seek professional help from a psychologist or therapist.

DISCUSSION

Spending too much time on the Internet, the child loses the boundary between the real and virtual world. As a result, internet addiction occurs. It is characterized by a strong desire in the child to be online, causing a desire not to want to spend time with family and friends, go to school and do homework. The child stops observing the external life, because he is under the influence of the virtual world, he does not want to be distracted - to leave this world.

If you pay attention, you can see that young people (especially teenagers) go internet cafes to play computer games with all kinds of subversive ideas. Can we say that such young people are fully using the Internet? The saddest thing is that many parents think that their children are learning when they are in front of computer. Children are also not afraid to deceive their parents. In fact, all this is the fault of indifferent parents.

Recently, I noticed a word in our dictionary, that is, "Igromania" - addiction to games. There are various positives and negatives on computers and phones, young people get addicted to games that waste their time. In addition, there is a phobia. "Nomophobia" - fear of being without a phone. Among teenagers, this phobia is so strongly developed that even you and I have this phobia.

According to experts, the number of users of the Internet system in our country is about 12.1 million, in other words, one third of the population of our republic regularly uses the Internet. It shows that there are opportunities to use quality communication systems in the implementation of the constitutional rights of our citizens, such as receiving, storing, and distributing information. People are using more and more different media channels. According to a GlobalWebindex survey, the average daily time that users between the ages of 16 and 60 can spend on different media channels:

1) The average time of using the Internet on a tablet, laptop or computer is 4 hours 42 minutes a day;

2) Average TV viewing time is 2 hours 21 minutes per day;

3) Average time of using social networks from different devices on the same day is 1 hour 53 minutes;

4) The average time of using the Internet on a smartphone is 1 hour 24 minutes a day.

Users often access the Internet using a computer, laptop or tablet. Most users access the Internet at work, at home, in transport and in nightclubs. It is not important to have close friends and acquaintances to access the Internet. Today, the majority of Internet users are young people, and a large part of them are students. Therefore, experts, doctors, pedagogues, and scientists emphasize that these new technologies have a negative impact on the education of children and youth if they are not given advice, instructions, or are not completely controlled. Because today's globalization process, the race to actively use various information fields to occupy the spiritual world of young people is accelerating. In order to prevent such a danger, first of all, it is necessary to form the culture of using the Internet among students in educational institutions.

CONCLUSION

On the flip side of the coin, the internet has many benefits, including online learning, remote work, shopping, learning, and news. Man creates everything himself and becomes a victim of himself, so it is appropriate to use everything in moderation. Let's protect our loved ones from becoming addicted to the Internet and from these currents and eddies. Because the fate and future of the Motherland is in the hands of young people like us. With this in mind, let's beware of distractions on the way to our goals!

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